

ENHANCING CARBON FIBRE PRODUCTION EFFICIENCY THROUGH LIFE CYCLE ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

Ever more stringent legislation and requirements to quantify impacts associated with a product, life cycle assessment methodology is becoming more relevant even in early stages of material development. A streamlined concept based on this methodology has been used to analyse in-depth the carbon fibre manufacturing process and different precursor material types on a large scale. The approach was designed to rapidly generate standardized results based on key process steps and parameters and thus enabled streamlined comparison of a number of process or material scenarios. Due to the secrecy of the carbon fibre industry, most publicly available information about the material and the production process is based on laboratory-scale research and implications of scaling up results are hardly ever discussed. This research addresses the still significant research gap on a large, continuous scale manufacturing, representative of industrial processes and connects them to laboratory scale experiments. The work highlights key areas of interest from an environmental and economical perspective to focus on when developing improved processes or precursor materials. Additionally, a more holistic picture of the carbon fibre manufacturing process was generated, by connecting process parameters, material properties, environmental implications, economic factors, and changes thereof. The work demonstrated that there is a parameter window, within which production processes can be optimized, but negative influences clearly limit this range. Finally, the comparison of different precursor materials showed certain advantages and disadvantages for all three materials, highlighting the importance of processability of the materials for advanced material properties. Similarly, the study showed the cost advantages an abundantly available source material can generate, although mechanical properties may not match more traditional materials typically used in industrial production today.

1 INTRODUCTION

Manufacturing industries across the globe face challenges related to global warming but also rising raw material and energy prices [1]. One of the main drivers for more restrictive laws and standards is the intention to reduce the effect of the changing climate worldwide [2, 3]. Recent global developments have highlighted the strong impact of energy supply in all areas of a products life cycle [4]. While these actions are noticeable in many areas, manufacturing industries are particularly affected [5]. Ever more restrictive legislation is forcing the manufacturing sector to continuously improve its environmental friendliness and track all impacts, driving the development and use of alternative materials that are more sustainable or promise an energy saving benefit over the product lifetime [6]. Carbon fibre reinforced components, for example, offer a significant weight reduction potential, as they are up to 35% lighter than aluminium and 60% lighter than commonly used steel [7]. The reduced weight in turn may decrease energy demand during the use-phase of vehicles for instance. There is, however, a significant hurdle for a more widespread success of this material, since the production of carbon fibre demands substantially more energy than the production of a comparable amount of steel or aluminium, for a product with closely similar properties [8]. Reducing environmental effects related to the used source material as well as process related effects and improving the overall cost of carbon fibre production are therefore important factors to increase its usage.

2 LIFE CYCLE ASSESSMENT-BASED ASSESSMENT CONCEPT

Life cycle assessment (LCA) is a well-established and standardized system analysis methodology to evaluate the environmental impacts of product systems [9, 10]. Advantages of LCA are its systemic perspective, and a holistic view on products from raw material extraction to recycling or disposal. Detailed assessments encompassing the whole product life cycle however, require a high level of expertise, are time-consuming and therefore difficult and expensive to perform. Streamlining and tailoring the assessment methodology in an iterative approach to quickly generate standardized results for carbon fibre production in early research stages can help uncover hot spots or facilitate early-on estimations for new material types. The aim is to reduce complexity and accelerate LCA application, while adhering to accepted principles.

To achieve this goal, a streamlined assessment methodology was devised to accelerate studies and minimize the need for extensive expert knowledge. Considering the high value of carbon fibre, a cost perspective was incorporated to provide a more holistic view. Primarily intended for use in the initial stages of material research and process development, particularly for material scientists and process developers with limited resources and experience in conducting Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) studies, this concept is not meant to fully replace standard adherent or more comprehensive assessment methodologies. Instead, it can be integrated into such studies to yield standardized values for comparison. However, it can also be utilized as a standalone tool to analyse different scenarios or obtain a quick estimate of energy demand, emissions, and costs [11]. Published studies on carbon fibre production based on LCA are often challenging to assess and compare due to variations in goals, scopes, and lack of detailed information on production setups [7, 12, 13]. The proposed streamlined iterative assessments, implemented from an early research stage, have the potential to enhance the development of carbon fibres by optimizing speed and cost efficiency, while focusing on ecologically and commercially viable innovations. In an industrial setting, this approach can be integrated with ongoing economic assessments for a more comprehensive perspective.

The proposed concept is specifically designed to provide parts of a full-scale assessment, where, through the standardized format, these outcomes are comprehensibly comparable. Figure 1 shows this modular core assessment intended for use in a carbon fibre production environment. The assessment process is predefined and divided into standardized modules, to streamline application. As a core concept, it is not meant to replace existing LCA or LCC methodology, but rather be integrated in assessment frameworks, as mentioned above [9-11]. The methodology can also easily be extended to include additional phases of production, e.g. precursor production or composite manufacture.

Figure 1 Modular LCA core assessment methodology

As LCA related knowledge often is limited in material focused research areas, a simple-to-use assessment methodology, which can be applied without the need of specialized software and intensive prior training, may increase acceptance and adaption. The concept presented here focuses on the carbon fibre manufacturing process gate-to-gate including upstream parts such as precursor manufacture or raw material extraction and downstream processing of the produced fibre material. Recycling processes were also not considered, as the low amounts of production waste typically are not yet recycled. In case of

larger production scenarios or an extended scope, post-production and consumer waste also have to be considered [11].

The assessment concept was subsequently used to examine the polyacrylonitrile-based carbon fibre production process on manufacturing step basis, showcasing the applicability of the model in a small-scale material research context. Mechanical and chemical analyses of fibre material for each production step were correlated with the evaluation of generated emissions. Material samples and exhaust gases were collected from the stabilization ovens, the low temperature (LT) and high temperature (HT) carbonization furnaces [14]. Three tows of 24,000 filaments each were processed at 30m/h for 48 min. at temperatures between 235 and 265°C in the stabilization ovens and for a further 5 min. at up to 1500°C in the carbonization furnaces.

The process was designed to produce carbon fibres with an estimated tensile strength of around 3.5 ± 0.7 GPa, a tensile modulus of approximately 253 ± 10 GPa, and a density of approximately 1.78 g/cm^3 . In this process, the fibre mass was reduced to about 55% compared to its initial weight per unit length, resulting in the overall yield of the carbon fibre production process (excluding sizing) falling within the range of reported values [15]. To gain further insights into the chemical changes and their impact on microstructure and properties, exhaust gases were assessed using an FT-IR gas analyser. However, due to the continuous addition of air to the stabilization ovens and nitrogen to the furnaces to replace exhaust gases, the precise input composition of the material could not be accurately determined. As a result, trace amounts of gases that are not direct by-products of the fibre material conversion process may be detected. Thus, this study specifically focused on the analysis of HCN, NH₃, CH₄, and CO, which are known to be direct by-products of the stabilization and carbonization processes. The Gas FT-IR analysis revealed that HCN was the predominant gas emitted throughout the entire fibre conversion process, with the majority (54%) being generated in the LT furnace, followed by the stabilization ovens (30%) and the HT furnace (16%). NH₃ was mainly emitted during the LT stage (90%), with the remaining 10% being generated during stabilization. CO was primarily produced in the LT furnace (65%), followed by 30% emitted during stabilization and a small amount of 5% in the HT furnace. Methane was only found in detectable amounts in the LT furnace.

Figure 2 Carbon fibre production emission assessment per 24k tow in g/h

The emissions produced during the stabilization phase, found to correlate with a consistent increase in mass density and significant chemical changes in the fibre. [14]. The high levels of HCN, NH₃, CO, and CH₄ measured during LT carbonization were consistent with the significant decrease in fibre mass observed during this stage. In the HT carbonization phase, the measured emissions showed slightly lower levels of the four gases compared to expected quantities. This was attributed to the generation and partial conversion of the measured emissions to less complex gases due to the high temperatures. CO₂, H₂, N₂, H₂O, and tar deposits were considered to be potential contributors to the HT emission composition. The FT-IR gas analysis results obtained for each production step exhibited good correlation with the observations for the entire manufacturing process.

These findings contributed to a better understanding of the relationships between the precursor material, chemical changes, and the emissions generated. These insights bring research closer to developing a comprehensive mass balance based on manufacturing data for the stabilization and carbonization process. It can also be utilized to identify potential improvements in incineration equipment and related gas, heat, or energy recovery systems. Furthermore, the data can be used to compare the impact of different processing conditions or precursor materials and guide research towards more cost-effective carbon fibre manufacturing methods [14].

3 ANALYSIS OF PROCESS PARAMETER VARIATION

Based on the developed assessment concept and the initial in-depth analysis of the carbon fibre production process, the methodology was applied to analyse the effects of changes made to the manufacturing process. To this end, material and process data was collected and compared for manufacturing scenarios with varying process speeds using the above-mentioned process analysis as a baseline. By optimizing the process parameters, temperature-time profiles were derived for four distinct production rates: "Slow" (1x), "Medium" (1.25x), "High" (1.5x), and "Fast" (2x). While the material properties were maintained at a similar level of approximately 3.54 GPa for tensile strength and 247.02 GPa for initial modulus, the overall energy demand and yield varied significantly [16]. In the stabilization stage, the temperature was raised by approximately 5°C for each zone as the line speed increased, while the processing time was reduced by 19%, 33%, and 50% for the "Medium", "High", and "Fast" trials, respectively. The low-temperature (LT) carbonization temperatures ranged from 400-550°C (Zone 1) to 750-950°C (Zone 3) for all four trials. The high-temperature (HT) carbonization zones were kept at the lowest possible processing temperatures. Although the HT furnace temperature remained constant for all trials, the heating rate from 1100 to 1300°C varied significantly as the line speed increased and residence time decreased.

Figure 3 Emissions per kg carbon fibre for different processing speeds

Gas emissions were monitored during each of the four trials to evaluate possible changes in gas composition or amounts with increasing processing speeds (Figure 3). The results from the slower three trials revealed that the concentration of emitted gases was solely dependent on the amount of material being processed and was not influenced by other process parameters. However, the "Fast" trial suggested that this trend may only be applicable within a limited temperature and processing time range.

Energy demand was continuously measured for all four trials, and in combination with the calculated yield from each trial, was converted to energy required per 1 kg of carbon fibre. Overall, a clear trend was observed in the stabilization section, where decreasing residence time (i.e., higher production speed) resulted in a decreased overall energy demand per material output, with the exception of the "Fast" production speed. This is particularly important as stabilization is considered to account for approximately 62% of the overall energy demand in the carbon fibre manufacturing process [17, 18]. The relatively small increase in the stabilization temperature profile of 5°C with increasing production speed did not cause a significant enough surge in energy demand to alter the overall trend. However, the LT carbonization stage showed that this is only true within a limited temperature range, as the significant temperature increase in this section from 400-550-750°C to 450-750-900°C, necessary to achieve the desired material properties, has a detrimental effect on energy demand when comparing it on a material output basis. The HT stage, due to no temperature changes, consistently showed a downward trend for shorter residence times, as expected. Throughout the analysis of all heat treatment steps, the "Fast" trial was an exception in terms of energy demand, driven by the lower overall yield (47%) compared to the other trials (55 ± 2%). [16].

Figure 4 Scaled-up overall energy demand and saving potential for three processing rates

The obtained results were subsequently modelled for industrial quantities based on baseline production quantities and energy demands reported by [17] and [18]. Figure 3 depicts how the data translated to savings for different production line capacities, where the yearly material output was correlated to overall energy demand. This shows the significant effect process optimization and tailoring to specific precursor material can have on energy demand, cost and environmental impact at larger scales, without the need for modifications to equipment or material.

The findings from this study highlighted significant energy-saving potential through exploring process limits and fine-tuning manufacturing conditions. This subsequently may result in lower energy demand and reduced emissions from energy generation, leading to a more environmentally friendly product. Despite the small rise in energy demand due to higher processing temperatures required at higher processing speeds, this work revealed that energy savings from higher material throughput per hour outweighed this increase, resulting in an overall decrease in energy demand per kg of final product and lower energy-related emissions. The "Fast" trial specifically demonstrated the impact of reduced material yield on energy demand per kg of final product.

These insights enhanced the understanding of the correlation between processing conditions, material properties, emissions, and energy demand, and pave the way for research towards cleaner production, reduced manufacturing costs in the stabilization and carbonization processes, and potential improvements in manufacturing equipment. One important conclusion is that precursor development focusing on polymer chemistry for faster processability may yield greater indirect environmental and cost benefits compared to reducing processing temperatures [16].

4 ANALYSIS OF MATERIAL INFLUENCE

Similarly the impact of three different precursor materials on energy demand, cost and environmental impact was analysed. The special grade polyacrylonitrile (PAN) precursor used in the previous sections was used again as reference material, as it is a commercially available precursor used in industrial carbon fibre production. Furthermore, a textile PAN, lacking specific processability-enhancing comonomers and an experimental Lignin/Cellulose blend were investigated. While the textile material promises a reduction in cost with a virtually identical manufacturing process, the Lignin/Cellulose blend offers a pathway to lower cost and environmental impact as the material is fully sourced renewably. Utilizing data from the continuous carbon fibre manufacturing process as outlined above for the special grade and textile PAN and early-stage experimental results for the bio-based material. Based on the material and process data collected and literature values, the energy demand, emission composition and cost were estimated.

Material properties, energy demand, emission composition and cost of the special grade PAN was found to be in the range of values reported elsewhere. Both the special grade PAN and the textile PAN reached mechanical properties of ≈ 3.0 GPa tensile strength and ≈ 210 GPa tensile modulus. These values were targeted as both commercially relevant and, in the case of the textile material, achievable. While the manufacturing process was the same for both acrylic materials in terms of process steps, the textile material needed to be processed significantly slower than the special grade material (stabilization time 96 min vs. 58 min). The theoretically estimated processing conditions for the lignin-cellulose blend [19, 20] significantly deviated from the other materials with a shorter stabilization of only 61 min, significantly longer carbonization times with as much as 30 min compared to 6 minutes for the special grade PAN. Additionally temperatures as high as 1600°C may be required to improve otherwise non-competitive material properties. As this is just a theoretical estimation based on recent literature and the process expected to not produce the same mechanical quality of material achievable with PAN, further research is needed once the process is more established and can be scaled up.

Thermogravimetric analysis was used to estimate the achievable yield for the three materials. At 1000°C the special grade PAN showed a residual mass of almost 56%, the textile PAN reached a close 50% while the bio-based blend only amounted to approx. 34% of its initial mass after heating. The results are in good agreement with reported values as well as measurements made on the larger scale trials [19, 21, 22].

The cost of textile PAN precursor is estimated to be approximately 56% lower than that of typically used special grade PAN. This research however suggested that processing costs during carbon fibre manufacture are significantly higher, as much as 176% in total, compared to PAN at the same scale and using equivalent equipment. This discrepancy is mainly due to significantly slower processing speeds

and lower yield owing to the less process-specific fibre chemistry [22]. The lower conversion rate also entails a higher process related environmental impact, as significantly more gasses are emitted, as high as 270% for HCN. To become a viable alternative for specialized precursor material, the processing of textile PAN needs to be improved, specifically achievable yield has to be increased as well as the tolerable processing speed. Another factor is the achievable material properties. While textile PAN-based carbon fibres can reach intermediate levels of properties, high strength (>4GPa) or high modulus applications (>300GPa) still require special grade precursor. The widely theoretical analysis of LignoCel showed that the material has a few significant shortcomings, which currently still inhibit commercial application. Most significantly the achievable material properties cannot match those of PAN-based fibres or even textile PAN based fibres. Furthermore, research is still in early stages to continuously process the material on anything larger than benchtop scale. However, as a bio-based material, the environmental impact is significantly better from the start than any fossil derived material. Moreover, as a low value by-product of other processes, the low material cost is unrivalled.

Figure 5 Cost comparison (in USD/kg) of PAN-, TexPAN- and Lignin-Cellulose-based carbon fibres

Figure 4 provides a cost comparison, with special grade PAN as reference representing the material with the highest total price, derived from data collected and previous research [22-25]. Based thereon, percentual changes in energy demand and (estimated) precursor prices were used to calculate the overall expected cost for textile PAN and the Lignin/Cellulose blend. Even though textile PAN shows a lower yield and needs longer processing, it is expected to be approximately 4 USD cheaper than PAN per kg carbon fibre. The Lignin/Cellulose blend, as a low value by-product of e.g. paper production, has the lowest precursor cost. This low price also translates to the lowest overall carbon fibre price with only 16.2 USD per kg, almost 25% less than special grade PAN.

Even though currently textile PAN-based, and more so, lignin/cellulose-based carbon fibres do not yet reach the material properties of special grade PAN-based carbon fibres, this research emphasises the potential of alternative materials to drive down the cost and environmental impact of carbon fibres, increase competitiveness of the material and penetrate into new, more cost or environmental sensitive markets.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The developed gate-to-gate assessment methodology proved a useful tool for evaluating a variety of processing conditions and precursor materials for a predefined carbon fibre manufacturing process. While based on LCA and LCC principles, the streamlined nature of the concept allowed for a rapid analysis of a large number of manufacturing scenarios and identification of optimal processing

conditions. At the same time the modularity enabled case-by-case adjustments to in- or exclude elements of the methodology and pivot towards specific key results, i.e. focus more on environmental impacts for one study and cost in the other.

Applying the developed assessment method to study the carbon fibre manufacturing process highlighted interrelationships between the material properties, process parameters, emissions and energy demand. This in turn demonstrated the relative contribution of each step in the processing chain to the environmental impact of the material and emphasized that energy production is more critical in terms of environmental impacts than any in-process off-gases.

The analysis of different manufacturing rates revealed that optimization towards an ideal balance of speed and aggressiveness of treatment can lead to significant energy and cost savings. The optimizations employed did not require any additional equipment or treatment and therefore showcase the importance of properly investigating the process and its limits when scaling to commercial production.

The comparison of different precursors showed that the material selection plays a key role in determining the overall environmental impact and cost of the final material. While manufacturing carbon fibre from alternative precursor materials, such as textile PAN or bio-based materials is significantly slower and more complex, benefits from the lower precursor material cost outweigh additional processing related costs. The environmental impact of textile PAN, however, was shown to be higher than for special grade PAN, while bio-based precursor was found to have the biggest environmental advantage.

Overall this work contributed to a better understanding of the carbon fibre manufacturing process on a continuous, industrial scale and highlighted areas of future focus in material or process development or when upscaling benchtop scale research.

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